

A force field of Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Cl^- , and SO_4^{2-} in aqueous solution based on the TIP4P/2005 water model and scaled charges for the ions

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Abstract

In this work, a force field for several ions in water is proposed. In particular we consider the cations Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} and the anions Cl^- , and SO_4^{2-} . These ions were selected as they appear in the composition of seawater and they are also found in biological systems. The force field proposed (denoted as Madrid-2019) is non-polarizable and both water molecules and sulfate anions are rigid. For water we use the TIP4P/2005 model. The main idea behind this work is to further explore the possibility of using scaled charges for describing ionic solutions. Monovalent and divalent ions are modeled using charges of 0.85 and 1.7, respectively (in electron units). The model allows a very accurate description of the densities of the solutions up to high concentrations. It also gives good predictions of viscosities up to 3 molal concentrations. Calculated structural properties are also in reasonable agreement with experiment. We have checked that no crystallization occurred in the simulations at concentrations similar to the solubility limit. A test for ternary mixtures shows that the force field provides excellent performance at an affordable computer cost. In summary, the use of scaled charges, which could be regarded as an effective and simple way of accounting for polarization (at least to a certain extent), improves the overall description of ionic systems in water. Finally, as it could be expected, the representation of the corresponding ionic crystals (or ionic melts) worsens with regard to full ionic charges force fields.

I. INTRODUCTION

On Earth, the overwhelming majority of water is found in oceans and seas. For this reason, more often than not, samples of water always contain a certain amount of solved salts. Since life started in the oceans it is not surprising that many of the ions present in the seas are also found in the living cells, though at lower concentrations. For this reason, it is clear that understanding ionic solutions is of fundamental interest in, at least, two important systems: oceans and living organisms. For these systems the typical conditions of interest are not too far away from the room temperature and room pressure (or for moderate pressures up to 1400 bar in deep water). However the composition often changes from one system to another. For this reason it is not possible to have experimental measurements of ionic solutions for a wide range of pressures, temperatures and compositions. Computer simulations could be useful to predict some of the properties and to understand the outcome of the experimental measurements.

In computer simulations the key factor controlling the accuracy of the predictions is the form of the intermolecular potential between the different species. This is usually denoted as the force field. In the 70's and 80's it was common to model ionic solutions using an implicit description of water. In this description, water was not included in the simulations, but rather its presence was taken into an implicit way by scaling the coulombic interactions between ions by the dielectric constant of water. Certainly in this treatment, simulations were quite fast, since water is the most abundant component in ionic solutions. This approach may be justified at very low concentrations when the ions are quite far apart but it will not work for moderate or high concentrations when the ions are closer. With the increase in computer power the simulation of ionic systems using atomistic models of water became more popular in the last 30 years.

Until recently, force fields for ionic solutions in water were mainly designed to reproduce experimental values of the hydration free energies and the first peak of the radial distribution functions (RDFs). In some cases, the lattice energies of the ionic crystal or quantum-mechanical data on ion-water clusters in the gas-phase were also taken into account. Polarizable and non-polarizable force fields have been proposed in the literature for alkali and alkaline earth halides.¹⁻²⁸ Quite often the force fields are based on non-polarizable water models as SPC,²⁹ SPC/E,³⁰ TIP3P,³¹ TIP4P,³¹ TIP4P-Ew,³² TIP4P/2005³³ but there

are also polarizable models as POL1,³⁴ RPOL,³⁵ SWM4-DP,^{36,37} B3K.³⁸ An overview of the force fields available up to 2011 can be found in Table I of the paper by Reif and Hunenberger¹⁹ and a set of possible target properties to be used for the validation of potential parameters is shown in Fig. 5 of the cited reference. A more recent review by Nezbeda et al.,³⁹ focussed on aqueous sodium chloride, discuss in detail the importance of the training set properties used to fit the force field parameters.

The need of a more broader check of the properties of these model systems was clearly underlined by Joung and Cheatham.¹⁵ These authors reported the formation of salt crystals well below the saturation limit in simulations of alkali halide aqueous solutions using different force fields. In fact, precipitation in NaCl,^{13,40–43} KCl,^{15,44} CaCl₂,⁴⁵ Na₂SO₄,⁴⁶ and Li₂SO₄⁴⁷ at concentrations below the solubility limit has been reported in simulation studies. Joung and Cheatham also provided some examples indicating that the anomalous crystallization had lead in fact to erroneous interpretations of the results of some previous computer simulations. It is thus important to ensure that the force field has a solubility limit as close as possible to the experimental value.

Unfortunately the calculation of the solubility by computer simulation is not a trivial task. It started in 2002 with the pioneering contribution of Ferrario et al.⁴⁸ who calculated the solubility limit of KF in water. In 2007 Sanz and Vega,⁴⁹ evaluated the solubility of NaCl. Other groups continued these calculations.^{50–54} After some initial discrepancies, a final agreement^{26,54,55} was found for two common force fields for NaCl in water, namely the Smith-Dang⁷ and the Joung-Cheatham models (both in SPC/E water). The solubility was 0.7 molal and 3.7 molal, respectively, to be compared with the experimental result of 6.1 m. Since the nucleation of crystallites is an activated process, the spontaneous precipitation is only observed at concentrations 4-5 times larger than the solubility limit. This fact, which could be viewed as an advantage, may also hide important inaccuracies of the force field.

In 2010 Kim et al.⁵⁶ pointed out that none of the tested rigid, non-polarizable models was able to reproduce the experimental trend for the concentration dependence of the diffusion coefficient of water in electrolyte solutions. Some of them even change the sign of the slope of the curves. They concluded that the form of the interaction potentials had to be reexamined. Similar conclusions were reached by Kann and Skinner.⁵⁷ Also recently it has been possible to determine activity coefficients for salts in water.⁵⁸ It has been shown that the activity coefficient of salt increases too quickly with concentration. Due to the

Gibbs-Duhem relation, this also means that the activity of water decreases too quickly —as compared to experiment— with the concentration of the salt. Since the activity of water controls all the colligative properties, one can not expect a good description of properties like cryoscopic descent, osmotic pressure and vapor pressures of salts solutions.

After these facts the scenario looks rather depressive. Moreover, if the situation of monovalent electrolytes is already bad, that of divalent ions as Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , SO_4^{2-} is even worse. Everything seems to point out that the inclusion of polarization is needed to describe ions in water. Notice that developing a good polarizable force field is not an easy task. If not parameterized with care sometimes a bad polarizable force field yields worse results than a properly optimized non-polarizable one. Since 2009, Leontyev and Stuchebrukhov^{59–64} published a series of papers that brought the last opportunity to non-polarizable force fields for ionic aqueous solutions. They proposed that maybe the charge of the ions should not be an integer number (in electron units), and that a scaled value should be used. They argued that non-polarizable models do not fully account for the electronic contribution to the dielectric constant and proposed that the screening effect of the electronic continuum could be effectively included by a simple scaling of the charges, namely, $q_{scaled} = q/\sqrt{\epsilon_{el}}$ where ϵ_{el} is the high frequency dielectric constant of water. This would lead to a scaled charge for monovalent ions of about 0.75. The use of scaled charges may find its justification as coming from the charge transfer and/or polarization of the water molecules around an ion.⁶⁵

The first paper of Leontyev and Stuchebrukhov in this line was not received with enthusiasm at the beginning. After all, for a chemist is difficult to accept scaled charges since the unscaled values have provided excellent results for ionic crystals and electrolyte solutions at infinite dilution. Jungwirth was probably the first to advocate this idea.^{45,47,66–68} Kann and Skinner⁵⁷ revisited the challenge of Kim et al.⁵⁶ and concluded that the scaling of the charges improved the description of the dynamical properties. Similarly, Yao et al.⁶⁵ have shown that the inclusion of dynamical charge transfer among water molecules accounts for the distinct behavior of the water diffusivity in $\text{NaCl}(\text{aq})$ and $\text{KCl}(\text{aq})$. In the same spirit, we have recently argued that the charges used in computer simulations describe the potential energy surface rather than the dipole moment surface,⁶⁹ an idea that has been further expanded by Jorge and coworkers.^{70,71} Even ourselves, after one year of efforts trying to optimize a model for NaCl using unit charges for the ions, adopted the proposal of Leontyev and Stuchebrukhov because of a simple argument: it seems to work. We thus proposed a

model for sodium chloride solutions, denoted as the Madrid model,⁷² using $q_{scaled} = 0.85$. Recently, in a study of the surface of a NaCl solution in water, Škvára and Nezbeda have shown that the results of the non-polarizable Madrid model and the polarizable AH/BK3 model²⁵ are found in most cases in mutual agreement.⁷³ Other work implementing the idea of charge scaling for electrolytes in water is that of Fuentes-Azcatl and Barbosa⁷⁴ who proposed a force field for NaCl using $q_{scaled} = 0.885$. Li and Wang^{75,76} have also applied the charge scaling concept to monovalent ions using $q_{scaled} = 0.804$. In summary, the number of groups following the suggestion of Leontyev and Stuchebrukhov is growing in recent years (see also Ref. 77 and 78)

Although it is clear that the description of ions in water may improve when polarization is included, it seems of interest to probe non-polarizable force fields using scaled charges. It is obvious that the scaling will have some limitations but it may be convenient to explore its limits before going to the polarizable models. The goal of this work is to develop a force field for ionic solutions in water based on the use of scaled charges for the ions. Since the performance of a force field for ions in water is related to the performance of the model chosen to represent the water interactions, it is essential to employ a satisfactory force field for water. In such a case good predictions of the solution properties will also be obtained at the infinite dilution limit. Among the rigid non-polarizable water models we have chosen TIP4P/2005, which provides an excellent description of a number of properties of liquid and solid water.^{79,80} For monovalent ions we use a scaled value of the charge, in particular, 0.85 (in electron units). This was our optimized value of the ionic charges in a recently developed model for NaCl in TIP4P/2005 water which is able to describe the NaCl aqueous solution quite accurately.

Here we extend the idea to other ions. The species selected in this work are essentially those typically found in seawater and biological fluids. In particular we will consider the monovalent cations Na^+ and K^+ (as well as Li^+) and the divalent cations Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} . For consistency, the scaled charges would be 1.7 in the latter case. With regard to anions, the most interesting ones seem to be Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} . The proposed force field is transferable in the sense that the water-ion and ion-ion interactions would be the same regardless of the composition of the system. In other words, the Cl-Cl or Cl-water interactions would be the same in NaCl, KCl, MgCl_2 or CaCl_2 aqueous solutions so that the force field could be used for any type of mixture.

The force field proposed in this work will be denoted as the Madrid-2019 force field. The target properties used to develop the force field were the solution densities, densities of the molten salts, radial distribution functions, contact ion pairs and hydration numbers. Solubility was not directly used as a target property. The main reason is that it has become clear recently that the use of the scaling of the charges does not lead to good estimates of the nucleation rate for salt crystallization.⁸¹ One should recognize from the very beginning that the scaling prevents an accurate description of the solid phase and/or the molten salts. The lack of transferability to other phases is the price to pay to improve the description of the solutions. We have taken into account solubility in an indirect way. We have checked that no spontaneous precipitation is observed at the experimental solubility limit after long simulation runs in large systems. We have also checked that the number of contact ion pairs (CIP) were always relatively low as we have recently shown that these figures should not be too high at the solubility limit.⁸² Thus, even though we can not guarantee that the proposed force field will reproduce the experimental values of the solubility limits, we can at least guarantee that the system will not precipitate at these concentrations, which otherwise would certainly invalidate the outcome of the simulations. We shall present results not only for pure salt solutions, but also for several ternary mixtures showing that the predictions are also quite reasonable for these independent test systems.

II. THE MADRID 2019 FORCE FIELD

We assume that the total energy of the system is given by the sum of the potential energy between the molecules/ions of the system (pairwise approximation). The interaction between any pair of atoms i, j of the system is given by a coulombic term plus a Lennard-Jones (LJ) potential:

$$V(r_{ij}) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{q_i q_j}{r_{ij}} + 4\epsilon_{ij} \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r_{ij}} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r_{ij}} \right)^6 \right]. \quad (1)$$

Here, ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity, q_i, q_j the charges of atoms i, j , ϵ_{ij} the energy minimum of the LJ potential and σ_{ij} the LJ diameter. Water is described by the TIP4P/2005 model.³³ This water model has a LJ interaction site at the oxygen and charges q_H , and q_M located respectively at the hydrogen positions and at a point M placed near the oxygen along the H-O-H bisector (see Table I). For monovalent ions (Na^+ , K^+ , Li^+ , Cl^-) the scaled value of the

charge is $|q_{scaled}| = 0.85$ since that was the choice for the Madrid model proposed previously.⁷² This choice was suggested by Kann and Skinner⁵⁷ and guarantees a good description of the infinite dilution properties of monovalent ions in TIP4P/2005 water since it compensates the low dielectric constant of the water model. For consistency, we assign a charge of 1.7 (in electron units) to monoatomic divalent cations (Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+}). Since we use scaled charges, the notation Na^+ (or Mg^{2+} , etc.) does not reflect the ionic charge. However, for simplicity, we respect throughout this paper the common ionic notation.

Modeling sulfate (a highly symmetric polyatomic anion) as a rigid body pose some problems when one intends to carry out molecular dynamics using constraints to preserve the molecular geometry. To avoid the inconveniences, the sulfur atom can not have mass and should be treated as a dummy atom. Of course, since the mass distribution does not affect the equilibrium thermodynamic properties within classical statistical mechanics, the sulfur mass can be distributed among the oxygens. In this way, the total molecular mass is preserved, so most of the dynamical properties will not be affected. It may slightly affect the rotation dynamics of the sulfate group. In summary, we have modeled sulfate as a set of four interacting sites at the positions of the oxygen atoms in a tetrahedral arrangement around a charged massless sulfur. The experimental molecular weight is then distributed among the four oxygens. In accordance to the choice for other ions, the net charge of the sulfate group is -1.7. There are several ways of distributing the net charge between the oxygen and sulfur atoms. We have found that a relatively wide range of values for the sulfur charge (q_S) may account of the properties of sulfate solutions although the parameters of the LJ interactions are slightly dependent on the particular choice of q_S . We have finally assigned it a charge of 0.90 (in electron units). The geometry of the sulfate molecules and the charges of the sites used in this work are presented in Table I.

TABLE I. Charges of the particles used in this work and geometric parameters of the water and sulfate molecules. Parameters for TIP4P/2005 water were taken from Abascal and Vega.³³

Particle charges/ e	
$q_{Na} = q_K = q_{Li} = 0.85, \quad q_{Mg} = q_{Ca} = 1.70, \quad q_{Cl} = -0.85$	
$q_S = 0.90, \quad q_{Os} = -0.65, \quad q_H = -q_M/2 = 0.5564$	
H ₂ O geometry	SO ₄ geometry
distance $d_{OH} = 0.9572 \text{ \AA}$	distance $d_{OS} = 0.149 \text{ \AA}$
distance $d_{OM} = 0.1546 \text{ \AA}$	distance $d_{OO} = 0.243316 \text{ \AA}$
Angle H-O-H=104.52°	Tetrahedral structure

We proceed now to describe how the parameters of the LJ interactions have been obtained. The order in which the parameters of the force field were optimized was as follows:

- Parameters of Na⁺ and Cl⁻.
- Parameters of cations (using the parameters of Cl⁻ obtained in the previous step) from studies of the corresponding cation chlorides.
- Parameters of SO₄²⁻ from studies of Na₂SO₄.
- Fine tuning of the K⁺-SO₄²⁻, Li⁺-SO₄²⁻ and Mg²⁺-SO₄²⁻ cross interactions from studies of the corresponding sulfate solutions.

The following set of target properties have been used to determine the optimal LJ interactions parameters for each salt:

- Densities of the aqueous solution at moderate (around 1 molal) and high concentrations (close to the solubility limit).
- Densities of the molten salt (at the experimental melting temperature) and of the solid at room temperature and pressure (only when the stable solid had the rock salt structure).

- Position of the main peak of the ion-water radial distribution function and hydration numbers.
- Number of contact ion pairs at a concentration near the experimental value of the solubility limit.

In Table II the experimental melting temperatures and solubility limits for the salts considered in this work are presented. As it can be seen, the solubility of all the salts (with the exception of CaSO_4) are moderate or high.

TABLE II. Experimental melting temperature for anhydrous salt⁸³ and salt solubility in water at 25 °C reported in molality units.^{84,85}

Salt	Melting temperature (K)	Solubility at 25 °C (m)
LiCl	883.15	19.95
NaCl	1073.85	6.15
KCl	1044.15	4.81
MgCl ₂	987.15	5.81
CaCl ₂	1048.15	7.3
Li ₂ SO ₄	1132.15	3.12
Na ₂ SO ₄	1157.15	1.96
K ₂ SO ₄	1342.15	0.69
MgSO ₄	1397.15	3.07
CaSO ₄	1733.15	0.02

Let us now expand a little bit our discussion on the target properties. The strongest forces in ionic systems come from electrostatic interactions, more in particular from the potential between unlike-charged particles which are somehow balanced by the repulsive forces at short distances. When ionic crystals are dissolved, the ions fall quite apart and the ionic interactions are much weaker and are replaced by the ion-water interactions. In both systems the interactions between non-identical particles (cation-anion, ion-water) are dominant. This

is in contrast with typical choices of force fields for non-ionic systems which usually define the parameters for the interactions between particles of the same type and evaluate the cross interactions using some (arbitrary) rules. Apart of the use of scaled charges, one of the main ideas behind this work is that the parameters associated with the cation-anion and ion-water interactions should be explicitly optimized. Since the charges of the particles are fixed, the optimization process mostly affects the σ_{ij} and ϵ_{ij} (with $i \neq j$) parameters of the Lennard-Jones potential. In this way, the density of the solution is paramount to determine the ion-water potential (notice that, given the excellent performance of TIP4P/2005, the departures of the solution densities from that of pure water provides a direct measure of the ion-water interactions). We have thus optimized the LJ parameters of the ion-water interactions in order to reproduce the density of moderate to high concentrated solutions.

On the other hand, we have used the densities of the molten salts as a target property. The inclusion of the melt is interesting because, in addition to the the more frequent interactions between unlike charged ions, in the melt there are also some contact between ions of the same type (this contact is not present in the solid). When developing the Madrid model for aqueous NaCl, we also considered the solid phase in the optimization process. However, here we have changed the approach in a qualitative way. Now we do not attempt to predict the exact experimental values of the densities neither of the melt nor of the solid. We recognize that models with scaled charges should not reproduce the experimental values (accurate predictions could only be obtained when using the full ionic charges). We observed that, typically, the density increases by about 20 per cent when the charge of the ions changes from 0.85 to 1 while keeping the LJ parameters. Thus, our target value for the density of the melt and/or the solid was around 20 per cent smaller than the experimental value.

As commented above cation-cation and/or anion-anion interactions have a minor impact in the final force field and we have usually accepted the values of previous works. In some cases (mostly for the interactions between ions of different type but carrying the same charge sign) we have used the Lorentz-Berthelot (LB) combining rules

$$\sigma_{ij} = \frac{\sigma_{ii} + \sigma_{jj}}{2}, \quad \epsilon_{ij} = \sqrt{\epsilon_{ii}\epsilon_{jj}}. \quad (2)$$

After these steps, we had a preliminary set of parameters which allowed us to compute the radial distribution functions of the aqueous solutions and calculate the position of the ion-water first peak, the CIP at high concentrations and the hydration numbers to check

if the overall results were reasonable. These calculations provided a feedback so the final refined parameters are the outcome of some trial and error methodology.

Our starting point was the recently proposed Madrid model, a force field for NaCl in water. However it was clear from the beginning that the densities predicted for MgCl_2 and CaCl_2 were slightly lower than the experimental ones. Since, in those attempts, we tried to optimize the parameters for Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} while keeping the parameters of Cl^- from the Madrid model that was suggesting that the contact distance between Cl^- and water was too large. We thus reduced the parameter $\sigma_{\text{Cl-Ow}}$ from the value in the Madrid model (0.426867) to 0.423867 nm. This is certainly a small change but, to keep the excellent predictions of Madrid model, it was necessary to slightly modify the rest of parameters. This new force field for aqueous NaCl is denoted as Madrid-2019 model and can be regarded as a minor modification of the original Madrid model (a comparison of the parameters of both models is given in the Supplementary material). In the results section we shall show that the performance of both models are essentially the same.

The parameters of the Madrid-2019 force field are presented in two separated Tables. The values of σ for the LJ interactions are given in Table III while the ϵ parameters are shown in Table IV. The geometry and charges were presented previously in Table I. When for a certain interaction one reads LB, it means that the corresponding value was obtained from the application of the LB combining rule, Eq. (2). When a + symbol is written in addition to the word LB, then it means that the LB rule has been validated in this work by the results of at least one mixture.

TABLE III. Lennard-Jones σ_{ij} parameters (in nm) for electrolyte solutions in TIP4P/2005 water containing Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} . Some σ_{ii} of cations were taken from the literature (Li^{15} , Na^{72} , Mg^{27} , Ca^{45} , O_w^{33} and S^{86}). In cases where a numerical value is not given, we suggest to follow Lorentz-Berthelot (LB) combination rules. LB(+) indicates that, in these cases, we have checked LB combining rules in binary or ternary solutions with satisfactory results. O_w and O_s denote the oxygen site in water and sulfate, respectively.

	Li	Na	K	Mg	Ca	Cl	O_w	S	O_s
Li	0.143970	LB(+)	LB	LB	LB	0.270000	0.212000	LB(+)	0.284485
Na		0.221737	LB(+)	LB(+)	LB(+)	0.300512	0.260838	LB(+)	LB(+)
K			0.230140	LB	LB	0.339700	0.289040	LB(+)	0.320000
Mg				0.116290	LB	0.300000	0.181000	LB(+)	0.240645
Ca					0.266560	0.315000	0.240000	LB	LB
Cl						0.469906	0.423867	LB(+)	LB(+)
O_w							0.315890	LB(+)	0.340445
S								0.355000	LB
O_s									0.365000

TABLE IV. As in Table III, but for Lennard-Jones ϵ_{ij} parameters (in kJ/mol).

	Li	Na	K	Mg	Ca	Cl	O _w	S	O _s
Li	0.435090	LB(+)	LB	LB	LB	1.282944	0.700650	LB(+)	0.803609
Na		1.472356	LB(+)	LB(+)	LB(+)	1.438894	0.793388	LB(+)	LB(+)
K			1.985740	LB	LB	1.400000	1.400430	LB(+)	LB (+)
Mg				3.651900	LB	3.000000	12.00000	LB(+)	2.748743
Ca					0.507200	1.000000	7.250000	LB	LB
Cl						0.076923	0.061983	LB(+)	LB(+)
O _w							0.774908	LB(+)	0.629000
S								1.046700	LB
O _s									0.837400

III. SIMULATION DETAILS

NVT and NPT molecular dynamics (MD) simulations have been performed using the GROMACS package.⁸⁷ In all runs the time step was 2 fs. The cut-off radii were fixed at 1 nm for both electrostatics and Lennard-Jones interactions. Long range corrections to the LJ part of the potential energy and pressure were included. Coulombic interactions were evaluated with the smooth PME method.⁸⁸ We have used the Nosé-Hoover thermostat^{89,90} with a relaxation time of 2 ps to keep a constant temperature, except in the case of solid state simulations where v-rescale algorithm⁹¹ has been selected. NPT simulations were performed at 0.1 MPa (and in some cases at 200 MPa) with Parrinello-Rahman pressure coupling⁹² with a relaxation time for the barostat of 2 ps. The LINCS algorithm^{93,94} has been used to constrain water geometry for most of the systems. In the case of salts containing the sulfate anion we used SHAKE⁹⁵ for both water and sulfate because this algorithm is more efficient for the sulfate group.

To calculate equilibrium properties like density or radial distribution function for liquid systems, we have performed simulations of 50 ns for a system containing 555 water molecules. This choice is useful because 10 ions of any type correspond to a 1 molal solution of that

ion. The number of contact ion pairs (CIP) can be computed from the cation-anion RDF as

$$n^{CIP} = 4\pi\rho_{\pm} \int_0^{r_{min}} g_{+-}(r) r^2 dr, \quad (3)$$

where g_{+-} is the cation-anion RDF and ρ_{\pm} is the number density of cation or anions. The integral upper limit r_{min} is the position of the first minimum in the RDF (if any) which must be located at a similar distance to that of the cation- O_w RDF. It is good idea to plot simultaneously the cation-anion and cation- O_w RDFs to determine if one is really evaluating the CIP or a solvent separated ion pair. To check for the absence of precipitation we typically performed a long run (of about 40 ns) for a system containing $555 \times 8 = 4440$ molecules of water and the corresponding number of ions to give the experimental value of the solubility limit and checked for aggregation.

The transport properties as viscosities and/or diffusion coefficient were also determined in a system having 4440 water molecules. The methodology used to compute the viscosity is similar to that described in previous works.⁹⁶ A previous NPT simulation is required to calculate accurately the volume of the system. After that, an NVT simulation was performed lasting between 50 ns and 200 ns. Throughout the run, the pressure tensor $P_{\alpha\beta}$ was calculated and saved on disk every 2 fs. Finally, the Green-Kubo formula was used:

$$\eta = \frac{V}{kT} \int_0^{\infty} \langle P_{\alpha\beta}(t_0) P_{\alpha\beta}(t_0 + t) \rangle_{t_0} dt. \quad (4)$$

The actual upper limit of the integral should be much higher than that of pure water. In fact, for some solutions, we have used values of the order of several hundreds of picoseconds (for pure water the upper limit is usually of the order of 10 ps).

The self-diffusion coefficient has been evaluated using the Einstein relation:

$$D = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{6t} \langle [\vec{r}_i(t) - \vec{r}_i(t_0)]^2 \rangle, \quad (5)$$

where $\vec{r}_i(t)$ and $\vec{r}_i(t_0)$ are the position of the i -th particle at time t and a certain origin of time t_0 and the $\langle [r_i(t) - r_i(t_0)]^2 \rangle$ term is the mean square displacement (MSD).

The densities of the melt and of the solid (with the rock salt structure) were obtained for systems containing 1000 ions. Simulations typically lasted 10 ns. For the melts the simulations were performed at 0.1 MPa and at the melting temperature of the anhydrous salt (see Table II). The simulations of the solid were performed at 298.15 K and 0.1 MPa for the salts exhibiting a NaCl solid structure: LiCl, NaCl and KCl. All these solids were found to be mechanically stable after a 10 ns run.

IV. RESULTS

A. 1:1 electrolyte solutions

1. Sodium chloride

As mentioned above, we realized soon in this research that setting the parameters of the chloride anion as in the original Madrid model did not allow to reproduce with high accuracy the densities of MgCl_2 and CaCl_2 solutions. That was possible when we decreased the σ_{Cl-O_w} parameter (0.003 nm). This slight change forced a fine tuning of the rest of parameters. The new Madrid-2019 model can be regarded as a minor modification of the original one (see the Supplementary Material). Fig. 1 shows the density predictions using different models for NaCl solutions. In the OPLS-TIP4P/2005,² and JC-TIP4P/2005,⁷² models the ionic parameters are those of the OPLS and Joung-Cheatham¹⁵ force fields, respectively, and the water model is TIP4P/2005. Since all these force fields use the same model for water, the differences in performance are due to differences the ion-water and ion-ion interactions. As can be seen in the plot, the calculations for the Madrid-2019 force field are in better agreement with the experimental data than those of OPLS-TIP4P/2005 and JC-TIP4P/2005. The results of this work are quite similar to those of the previous Madrid model although we notice a slight improvement in the 200 MPa isobar at high concentrations.

FIG. 1. Density as a function of molality for aqueous NaCl solutions at $T = 298.15$ K for the 0.1 MPa and 200 MPa isobars. Values from this work are shown with blue circles, the Madrid model predictions⁷² are the red circles, and the results for the OPLS-TIP4P/2005² and JC-TIP4P/2005⁷² force fields are represented by a green triangle and orange square symbols, respectively. The experimental data⁹⁷⁻⁹⁹ are shown as a continuous line.

In Table V densities for solid (at 0.1 MPa and 298.15 K) and molten salts (at 0.1 MPa and the experimental melting temperature) are presented. For each system two results are shown. The first one corresponds to the density of the Madrid-2019 force field using the scaled charges q_{scaled} . The second one shows the density obtained with the same set of parameters as in the Madrid-2019 model but replacing the scaled charges by the standard values q (i.e 1 for monovalent and 2 for divalent ions). The densities of the molten NaCl using the Madrid-2019 force field is a 15 percent lower than in experiment. Concerning the density of the crystal the result of our model is about 5 per cent below the experimental one. These departures greatly decrease when the scaled charges are replaced by the full ones. This fact seems to indicate that the relative size of the ions is well captured by the parameters presented in Table III and IV for the ion-ion interactions. In other words, the removal of water from the solution translates into a change of the effective ionic charges from those used in this work to the usual integer numbers in the crystal or the melt. In this way, the non-transferability of the force field between the solution and the pure salt in

condensed state is the price to pay for a better description of the solution properties. Notice finally that the results of Table V indicate that the comments made here for NaCl may be extended to other salts: the typical deviations between the scaled charged model and the full charged ones are less than a 20 percent for the melts and less than a 5 percent for the crystal.

For the sulfate molecules we are not presenting results with the unscaled charges as there are many ways of distributing the charge between the oxygen and the sulfate to achieve a net charge of -2.

TABLE V. Densities of the molten salts (at 0.1 MPa and the experimental melting temperature⁸³) and of the anhydrous salt crystals (at 0.1 MPa and 298.15 K). Values of this work are given under columns labelled q_{sc} and q which are obtained using scaled charges and total charges for the ions, respectively.

Salt	Melt density			Solid density		
	q_{sc}	q	Expt	q_{sc}	q	Expt
LiCl	1237	1443	1502	1907	2075	2068
NaCl	1331	1634	1556	2050	2218	2165
KCl	1236	1531	1527	1834	1984	1984
MgCl ₂	1581	1779	1680			
CaCl ₂	1754	2083	2085			

To gain further evidence of the quality of the Madrid-2019 force field we have analyzed some structural results. We have computed the ion-ion and ion-water radial distribution functions at 6 m, a concentration close to the experimental value of the solubility limit. From the RDF it is possible to evaluate the number of contact ion pairs (see Eq. (3)) and the hydration numbers (i.e the number of water molecules around each ion). The latter are computed as in Eq. (3) but replacing ρ_{\pm} by ρ_w and $g_{+-}(r)$ by $g_{ion-O_w}(r)$ instead. The results are summarized in Table VI and compared with experimental X-ray and neutron diffraction data collected in the work of Marcus.¹⁰⁰ The number of CIP is an important property when studying electrolytes. A high value provides an indirect indication of cluster formation and/or precipitation of the salt. For 1:1 electrolytes with solubility lower than

10 m, Benavides et al.⁸² suggested that the number of CIP must be below 0.5 to be sure that precipitation and/or aggregation of ions has not occurred. For NaCl we have found a value of 0.17 at 6 m. In fact aggregation was not found at this concentration in long runs of large systems. The hydration numbers for Na⁺ and Cl⁻ are 5.4 and 5.9 waters, respectively. These values are within the range reported in experiments.¹⁰⁰ The d_{Na-O_w} and d_{Cl-O_w} distances are, 2.25 Å and 3.10 Å, respectively, to be compared to the experimental estimations 2.33 Å, and 3.05 Å.

TABLE VI. Structural properties for 1:1 electrolyte solutions at 298.15 K and 0.1 MPa. Number of contact ions pairs (CIP), hydration number of cations (HN_c) and anions (HN_a), and position of the first maximum of the cation-water (d_{c-O_w}), and anion-water (d_{a-O_w}) RDFs. In parentheses, experimental data taken from the work of Marcus¹⁰⁰ and references therein. Properties were calculated for LiCl, NaCl, and KCl solutions at 12 m, 6 m, and 4.5 m concentration, respectively.

Salt	CIP	HN_c	HN_a	d_{c-O_w} (Å)	d_{a-O_w} (Å)
LiCl	0.01	4(3.3-5.3)	5.9(4-7.3)	1.84(1.90-2.25)	3.03(3.08-3.34)
NaCl	0.17	5.4(4-8)	5.9(5.5-6)	2.33(2.41-2.50)	3.05(3.08-3.20)
KCl	0.38	6.5(6-8)	5.8(6-8)	2.73(2.60-2.80)	3.03(3.08-3.16)

Two transport properties have been evaluated in this work: the shear viscosity and the self-diffusion coefficients. Fig. 2 shows the shear viscosity for NaCl aqueous systems as a function of the concentration at 298.15 K and 0.1 MPa. The results of the Madrid-2019 force field are again quite similar to those of the Madrid force field. In general, the agreement with experimental data is excellent at low concentrations. The dependence with temperature follows the same trend as the experimental one but the slope is somewhat overestimated, especially at very high concentrations. Anyway, our model improves considerably the results for JC-TIP4P/2005. This confirms that the scaling of the charges leads to a better description of the viscosity of NaCl(aq).

FIG. 2. Shear viscosity curves as a function of concentration for aqueous LiCl, NaCl, and KCl systems at 298.15 K and 0.1 MPa. Result from this work are shown with blue circles, those from Madrid model⁷² with red circles, JC-TIP4P/2005⁵⁵ in orange squares. The continuous line is our fit of experimental data taken from Refs. 101 and 102 and references therein. NaCl and LiCl values were shifted up one and three units, respectively, for better legibility.

Numerical results for the self-diffusion coefficients of ions and water are presented in Table VII. The cation and anion self-diffusion coefficients were evaluated at two different concentrations (0.5 m and 1 m) to provide an idea of the value at low concentrations so that they can be compared to the experimental ones at infinite dilution.¹⁰³ The diffusivity of Na^+ seems to be in accordance with the experimental measurements but that of Cl^- differs to a certain extent from experiment. Finally, the performance of the force field for the ratio $D_w^{\text{salt}}/D_w^{\text{pure}}$ is quite good.

TABLE VII. Self-diffusion coefficients of cations and anions (D_c, D_a) as a function of concentration (in $10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$ units) for electrolyte water solutions at 298.15 K and 0.1 MPa. Comparison is done with experimental results at infinite dilution.¹⁰³ Water diffusion in electrolyte solutions relative to water diffusion in pure water, D_w^{salt}/D_w^{pure} , is also shown. Experimental data at 1 m were taken from Müller and Hertz,¹⁰⁴ where $D_w^{pure} = 2.3$ and in our simulation $D_{TIP4P/2005}^{pure} = 2.14$ without applying the finite-size correction of Yeh and Hummer.¹⁰⁵

Salt	D_c			D_a			D_w^{salt}/D_w^{pure}	
	Sim		Expt	Sim		Expt	Sim	Expt
	1 m	0.5 m	0 m	1 m	0.5 m	0 m	1 m	1 m
LiCl	0.81	0.92	1.03	1.31	1.38	2.03	0.84	0.91
NaCl	0.99	1.22	1.33	1.33	1.39	2.03	0.89	0.94
KCl	1.63	1.70	1.96	1.52	1.45	2.03	0.97	1.03
MgCl ₂	0.41	0.64	0.705	0.89	1.30	2.03	0.67	0.73
CaCl ₂	0.55	0.63	0.791	1.10	1.23	2.03	0.74	0.82
Li ₂ SO ₄	0.63	0.82	1.03	0.68	0.72	1.07	0.74	
Na ₂ SO ₄	0.82	0.85	1.33	0.76	0.91	1.07	0.79	
K ₂ SO ₄	–	1.60	1.96	–	0.86	1.07	–	
MgSO ₄	0.40	0.59	0.705	0.58	0.78	1.07	0.72	

In summary, the main conclusion of the calculations for NaCl solutions is that the Madrid-2019 model yields quite similar results to those obtained with the original Madrid model for equilibrium, structural and transport properties. We thus believe that other properties non evaluated in this work will follow a similar pattern (for a more comprehensive discussion of the performance of the Madrid model we refer the reader to our previous work⁷²).

As it has been previously reported (Fuentes-Azcatl and Alexandre), the TIP4P/2005 model does not reproduce the experimental values for the dielectric constant of the pure water, so that it is expected that the variation of the dielectric constant in function of the salt concentration also fails. Knowing this fact, we have explored the behavior of the reduced relative dielectric constant $\Delta\epsilon_r \equiv (\epsilon_{solution} - \epsilon_{water})/\epsilon_{water}$

FIG. 3.

2. Potassium chloride

The densities of potassium chloride solutions are shown in Fig. 4. The agreement with experimental data is excellent along the whole concentration range. The relative failure of MP-S/E3B model which also uses scaled charges⁵⁷ is in probably due to the fact that the model underestimates the water density. For a concentration of 4.5 m, the K- O_w RDF shows a first peak at 2.73 Å and the hydration number of K is 6.5 water molecules. At this concentration the maximum in the Cl- O_w RDF is located at 3.03 Å and the corresponding coordination number is 5.8 water molecules, very similar to that in LiCl and NaCl solutions. As for NaCl, the structural results are in accordance with the experimental estimations. At the highest simulated concentration the CIP takes an acceptable value of 0.38 without cluster formations during the whole simulation. In contrast, precipitation of KCl has been reported in previous work when using models with full ionic charges.⁴⁴

FIG. 4. Density as a function of molality at $T = 298.15$ K and 0.1 MPa for two 1:1 electrolyte aqueous solutions, LiCl and KCl. The symbols are as follows. Blue circles: this work, red squares: JC-TIP4P-Ew,¹⁵ orange diamonds: JC-TIP4P/2005,¹⁰⁶ green triangles: MP-S/E3B.⁵⁷ The continuous line is our fit of experimental data taken from Refs. 101 and 107 and references therein. KCl values were shifted up 50 units for better legibility.

The viscosities of KCl solutions were already shown in Fig. 2 together with the results for other 1:1 electrolytes. The comparison with experiment is quite remarkable, especially because the model correctly predicts the small dependence of η on concentration. The diffusion coefficients of the cation at 1 m and 0.5 m (see Table VII) seem to point toward the experimental value at infinite dilution. As to the Cl^- anion, despite that there is some improvement in the self-diffusion respect to LiCl and NaCl cases, the results of the model are clearly lower than those from experiment. On the other hand, the presence of KCl does not affect much the diffusion coefficient of water (the relative water diffusion at 1 m is 0.97). In experiments the same is true, although the salt changes the diffusion coefficient in the opposite direction as it increases to 1.03 (this tendency is correctly described by the MP-S/E3B model⁵⁷).

3. *Lithium chloride*

Fig. 4 shows the equation of state for LiCl in water 298.15 K and 0.1 MPa compared to experiment and to the results of other force fields. The performance of the Madrid-2019 is better than that of the MP-S/E3B model which also use scaled charges. Results for force fields that do not use the concept of charge scaling are also presented, in particular, for JC/TIP4P-Ew,¹⁵ and its modified version¹⁰⁶ which replaces the TIP4P-Ew water model by TIP4P/2005. The predictions of the Madrid-2019 force field are in excellent agreement with experimental data. Although slight deviations may be noticed at very high concentrations, the departure from experiment at 12 m is less than 1%. In contrast, the results of the rest of force fields are not accurate enough at low concentrations and, in the case of JC/TIP4P-Ew, it predicts a much less steeper slope.

Some structural results for a 12 m concentration were presented in Table VI . The CIP are very low at this concentration. This is probably due to a strong hydration layer which prevents close cation-anion contacts. The Li^+ ions are hydrated with four water molecules which is consistent with the experimental values.¹⁰⁰ In line with other monovalent halides, the hydration number of Cl^- is 5.9. The ion-water distances at the first maximum of the RDF seem a bit underestimated, about 3% below the experimental estimations. More consistent results were found for other models, see Table VIII in the work of Kann and Skinner.⁵⁷

The Madrid-2019 model exaggerates the dependence of the viscosity with concentration (see Fig. 2). This is a common trend for all 1:1 electrolytes although it seems that the deviation between simulation and experiment becomes larger as the size of the cation becomes smaller. It is to be noticed that the differences between simulation and experiment are much larger for models with full ionic charges. Thus, the charge scaling alleviates but does not correct completely the dependence of the viscosity on salt concentration. Concerning the values of the diffusion coefficient of Li at infinite dilution, the results obtained in this work seem reasonable as compared to the experimental value at infinite dilution. Notice that the differences between the diffusion of the chloride anion in NaCl, KCl and LiCl solutions are quite modest suggesting that the effect of the counter ion is small at low concentrations. The predictions for the water diffusion agree reasonably with the experimental data, the discrepancy is about a 8% (see Table VII).

B. 2:1 electrolyte solutions

1. Magnesium chloride

Fig. 5 presents the densities of MgCl_2 solutions at 298.15 K and 0.1 MPa. The agreement with the experimental data is quite good. At high concentrations the deviations are of about 1 %. The results obtained with the OPLS force field in combination with TIP4P/2005 are also shown for a concentration of 3 m. The deviation from experiment is quite noticeable for this model that uses full ionic charges.

FIG. 5. Density curves for MgCl_2 and CaCl_2 in water solutions at 298.15 K and 0.1 MPa. Blue circles are the data from this work, green triangles are the MFN-SPC/E results,²³ and red squares represent the calculations for the OPLS-TIP4P/2005 model. The continuous line is our fit of experimental data taken from Refs. 102 and 107 and references therein. For a better appraisal, the CaCl_2 densities have been shifted up 100 units.

Structural properties at 5 m and are summarized in Table VIII. The hydration sphere around the Mg^{2+} contains exactly six water molecules. No anions are able to enter within the hydration shell of the cations (hence the CIP is 0) meaning that the interaction between Mg^{2+} and water is very strong. This is a well known result. Not surprisingly MgCl_2 often precipitates as an hexahydrate. The second hydration shell is found at 4.18 Å with a

coordination number of 13 waters in agreement with values reported in literature (see Table 3 in the work of Zhang et al.¹⁰⁸). The hydration number for Cl^- is 5.9 in agreement with experiment. For both cation and anion, the position of the first peak of the ion- O_w RDF lie at a shortest distance than the experimental estimations. This deserves a comment. It is somewhat surprising that, even though the model is able to reproduce extraordinary well the density of both pure water and the solution, the distance of the ions to the oxygens in the first hydration shell is smaller than that reported from scattering experiments. It should be pointed out that extracting individual RDF from scattering data is not a trivial task (especially in electrolyte solutions where one has contributions from many species). Even for pure water, experimental results for the RDF are improved year after year. For this reason at this point we believe that these experimental data should be regarded with care. This problem might be revisited in the future. In fact it would be of interest to compute the structure factor from the simulations of this work and to see if they are able to describe the experimental data.

TABLE VIII. As in Table VI but for 2:1 electrolyte solutions. Properties in solution were calculated at 5 m and 6 m for MgCl_2 and CaCl_2 , respectively. CIP is just the number of anions in contact with the cation.

Salt	CIP	HN_c	HN_a	$d_{c-O_w}(\text{\AA})$	$d_{a-O_w}(\text{\AA})$
MgCl_2	0	6(6-8.1)	5.9(6)	1.92(2.00-2.11)	3.03(3.13-3.16)
CaCl_2	0.02	7.1(5.5-8.2)	6.2(5.8-8.2)	2.38(2.39-2.46)	3.03(3.12-3.25)

Fig. 6 displays the concentration dependence of the viscosity of MgCl_2 solutions. The Madrid-2019 model is able to describe the experimental behavior up to 3 m concentration but beyond this concentration the deviation from experiment is significant. Since viscosities can be measured with great accuracy, all the evidence presented so far points out that although the scaling of the charge provides a reasonable description of transport properties up to moderately high concentrations, the model fails at very high salt (though much less than models that use full ionic charges). Something is going on at high concentrations that is not captured by the force field of this work (and probably for the rest of the force fields proposed so far). This is a point that require further work.

FIG. 6. Shear viscosity as a function of molality for aqueous MgCl_2 and CaCl_2 solution at 298.15 K and 0.1 MPa. Result from this work are shown with blue circles and the continuous line is our fit of experimental data taken from Refs. 101 and 102 and references therein. MgCl_2 values were shifted up ten units.

As to the diffusion of Mg^{2+} (see Table VII), our results at 1 m and 0.5 m concentrations extrapolate nicely to the experimental data at infinite dilution. The model also captures quite well the sizable decrease in the diffusion coefficient of water when adding MgCl_2 . Experimentally the diffusion coefficient of water in a 1 m solution decreases to a 73%, to be compared to the prediction of the Madrid-2019 force field which yields 67%.

2. Calcium chloride

The densities of calcium chloride solutions are displayed in Fig. 5. The performance of the Madrid-2019 model is excellent up to 4 m. The deviations from experiment increase slightly with the salt concentration but they never exceed a 1%. Also included in the plot are the data reported by Mamatkulov et al.²³ here denoted as MFN-SPC/E. The discrepancies from experiment are now important and exceed a 5 percent at high salt. The hydration number of Ca^{2+} is 7.1 water molecules (see Table VIII). The increase respect to that of Mg^{2+} is brought about by the increase in the cation size. In fact, the maximum of the Ca-O_w RDF

appears at a higher distance, 2.38 Å, than in the lighter divalent cation. This distance is just at the lower limit of the range reported for experiments. The simulations of calcium chloride solution confirms that the hydration of the chloride anion is essentially insensitive to the counterion. Only the coordination number, 6.2, is marginally different.

The predictions for the viscosity of aqueous CaCl_2 follow a similar trend to those for MgCl_2 . The model does a good job up to 3 m and fails beyond this salt concentration (although the deviations from experiment are now somewhat smaller). The diffusion coefficients of Ca^{2+} in water seem to approach the experimental value at infinite dilution (see Table VII). The model also accounts quite acceptably for the experimental drop of the diffusivity of the water molecules in a 1 m solution (18 *vs* 26 per cent). Finally, it is worth noting that the force field proposed in this work captures correctly the fact that, at 1 m concentration, the diffusion of water in 1:1 electrolytes decreases by about a 5 per cent whereas the change is about a 20 per cent for 2:1 electrolyte solutions.

C. 1:2 electrolyte solutions: lithium, sodium and potassium sulfates

Before commenting the results for these systems, it is interesting to point out that the properties of sodium sulfate were used to optimize the sulfate parameters (fixing the Na parameters as obtained from NaCl systems). These parameters were mostly fixed for the rest of sulfates. In fact, we only modified slightly the LJ parameters of the cation- O_s interaction and accepted the LB rule for other cross interactions.

Fig. 7 shows the densities of the sulfates of monovalent cations as predicted by the Madrid-2019 force field. They are in excellent agreement with experiment although small deviations are visible at high concentrations in the case of Li_2SO_4 .

FIG. 7. Density as a function of salt concentration for Li_2SO_4 , Na_2SO_4 , and K_2SO_4 aqueous solutions at $T=298.15$ K and 0.1 MPa. Blue circles are the results from this work and the continuous line is our fit of experimental data taken from Refs. 102, 107, and 109 and references therein. Data for Na_2SO_4 and K_2SO_4 are shifted up 100 and 200 units, respectively.

Table IX collects the structural results obtained for 1:2 electrolytes with the sulfate as the anion. As also observed in 1:1 electrolytes, the hydration of sulfate solutions is strongly dependent of the cation size. No contact ion pairs are found for the smallest cation which explains the hygroscopic properties of lithium sulfate. The CIP of sodium sulfate is already significant, 0.37, and that of the potassium sulfate reaches a considerable value, 0.88. We did observe neither aggregation nor precipitation at the highest concentration of these salts, even after long runs. The hydration numbers and the location of the cation- O_w peaks are almost exactly the same as those found previously in chloride solutions.

The solvation shell of SO_4^{2-} is formed by about 13 water molecules, irrespective of the accompanying cation. Similar values have been reported in previous MD simulations.^{86,110,111} In contrast, the experimental value is much lower, about 7. Given the enormous size of the sulfate anion, it is difficult to believe that it is hydrated by just 7 molecules of water.¹¹¹ The positions of the first maximum of the $\text{S}-O_w$ and the O_S-O_w RDFs (which once again are independent of the corresponding counterion) are in reasonable agreement with the experimental values.

TABLE IX. As in Table VI but for 1:2 electrolyte solutions. Properties in solution were calculated for Li_2SO_4 , Na_2SO_4 and K_2SO_4 at 3 m, 1.5 m and 0.6 m, respectively. CIP is just the number of cations in contact with the sulfate group.

Salt	CIP	HN_c	HN_a	$d_{c-O_w}(\text{\AA})$	$d_{S-O_w}(\text{\AA})$	$d_{O_s-O_w}(\text{\AA})$
Li_2SO_4	0	4(3.3-5.3)	13(6.4-8.1)	1.84(1.90-2.25)	3.75(3.67-3.89)	3.00(2.84-2.95)
Na_2SO_4	0.37	5.5(6)	13(6.4-8.1)	2.33(2.41-2.50)	3.75(3.67-3.89)	3.02(2.84-2.95)
K_2SO_4	0.88	6.5(6-8)	12(6.4-8.1)	2.73(2.60-2.80)	3.75(3.67-3.89)	3.02(2.84-2.95)

A look at Table VII indicate that the extrapolation of our simulated results for the diffusion coefficient of Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , and SO_4^{2-} in sulfate solutions are in overall reasonable agreement with the reported experimental data at infinite dilution (although, very likely, the value for Li^+ is a bit low). We are not aware of experimental data on the diffusion coefficient of water in sulfate solutions. Our results show that, in accordance with the behavior in other electrolyte solutions, the presence of salt significantly reduces the diffusion of the water molecules.

The dependence of the viscosity of sulfate solutions on the salt concentration is shown in Fig. 8. The agreement between the results of the Madrid-2019 force field and the experimental ones is quite good for K_2SO_4 and Na_2SO_4 . Certainly, given the relatively low solubility of these salts, the comparison is made for concentrations where the presence of ions does not affect dramatically the viscosity. Our model gives only a fair description of the viscosity of Li_2SO_4 solutions. Even at 1.5 m concentration, the departure from experiment is much more significant than for Na_2SO_4 . Since the slope of the simulation data is largely underestimated, the result at the solubility limit is almost one half the experimental value.

FIG. 8. Shear viscosity as a function of concentration for aqueous Li_2SO_4 , Na_2SO_4 , and K_2SO_4 systems at 298.15 K and 0.1 MPa. Results of this work are shown as blue circles and the continuous line is our fit of experimental data taken from Refs. 101 and 102 and references therein. Values for Na_2SO_4 and Li_2SO_4 solutions were shifted up one and two units, respectively.

D. 2:2 electrolyte solutions: magnesium sulfate

The equation of state of magnesium sulfate solutions is plotted and compared to experimental results in Fig. 9. The agreement is very good. Only at high salt the simulations results underestimate the experimental density (about 1% at 2.5 m).

FIG. 9. Density as a function of molality for MgSO_4 solutions at 298.15 K and 0.1 MPa. In blue circles, data from this force field. The continuous line is our fit of experimental data taken from Refs. 102, 107, and 109 and references therein.

Structural properties for a 2.5 molal solution are presented in Table X. Again the magnesium is surrounded by 6 molecules of water located at a distance of 1.92 Å and the sulfate anions are surrounded by 13.5 molecules of water at 3.75 Å. Also, the strong hydration layer disables the formation of contact ion pairs. At this concentration no cluster aggregation is observed in simulations of large systems for long times.

TABLE X. As in Table VI but for a 2.5 m MgSO_4 solution.

Salt	CIP	HN_c	HN_a	$d_{c-O_w}(\text{Å})$	$d_{S-O_w}(\text{Å})$	$d_{O_s-O_w}(\text{Å})$
MgSO_4	0	6(6)	13.5(6.4-8.1)	1.92(2.00-2.11)	3.75(3.67-3.89)	3.00(2.84-2.95)

In Fig. 10 the viscosity for magnesium sulfate in water is shown. The simulation results are well below the experimental ones and the departures increase with concentration, a feature that was also found in MgCl_2 . As with other salts containing a divalent ion, the diffusion coefficient of water in a 1 m solution decreases significantly respect to that of pure water (see Table VII).

FIG. 10. Shear viscosity as a function of molality for MgSO_4 solutions at 298.15 K and 0.1 MPa. Blue circles are the data from this work and our fit of experimental data taken from Refs. 101 and 102 (and references therein) is represented as a continuous line.

E. Ternary mixtures

In order to test and validate the force field of this work we here present results for ternary mixtures of electrolytes (i.e two salts and water). We use LB rules for those interactions that were not determined in the optimization process (see Tables III and IV). The calculations were done for a sample made of 555 water molecules and adjusting the number of salt molecules to the corresponding experimental concentration. Results for the Madrid-2019 force field are presented in Table XI together with experimental data.^{112–116} The performance of the model is excellent. Some small deviations are in part due to the slight different concentration from the simulations as compared to the experimental ones. Of course the difference in concentration could be alleviated by using a larger system in the simulation. However, since our primary goal is to validate the proposed force field in systems not used in the optimization process, this test is already sufficient. The main advantage of presenting a force field is that it can deal with system of arbitrary compositions, pressures and temperatures.

TABLE XI. Densities for ternary solutions at 298.15 K and 0.1 MPa rounded to entire units in kg/m³. Experimental data from Refs. 112–116. m_1 and m_2 are the molalities of the salts labelled as (1) and (2), respectively. $m_{tot} = m_1 + m_2$ is the total concentration.

Expt			This work			Expt			This work		
m_{tot}	m_1/m_2	Density	m_{tot}	m_1/m_2	Density	m_{tot}	m_1/m_2	Density	m_{tot}	m_1/m_2	Density
NaCl (1) + LiCl (2) + H ₂ O						NaCl (1) + KCl (2) + H ₂ O					
2.106	0.4835	1057	2.1	0.50	1053	0.7935	0.3325	1032	0.8	1/3	1032
2.041	0.7253	1058	2.1	0.75	1056	2.3760	2.9867	1088	2.4	3	1089
1.976	1.0880	1059	1.9	10/9	1054	3.9943	0.3325	1148	4	1/3	1149
1.846	2.9013	1062	1.9	2.80	1060	4.6241	1.0010	1164	4.6	1	1164
NaCl (1) + MgCl ₂ (2) + H ₂ O						NaCl (1) + CaCl ₂ (2) + H ₂ O					
1.0992	9.9811	1044	1.1	10	1043	0.4060	0.3334	1028	0.4	1/3	1028
3.5006	5.9942	1138	3.5	6	1136	2.0102	3.0218	1094	2	3	1094
3.5099	0.1660	1210	3.5	1/6	1207	2.8055	1.0001	1158	2.8	1	1158
4.0106	0.3327	1224	4	1/3	1221	4.0519	3.0218	1178	4	3	1176
NaCl (1) + Na ₂ SO ₄ (2) + H ₂ O											
0.5997	0.2001	1062	0.6	0.2	1062						
1.5000	1.9991	1092	1.5	2	1092						
1.9958	1.0026	1143	2	1	1142						
3.4999	5.9983	1155	3.5	6	1154						

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work a new force field (denoted as Madrid-2019) for several ions in water has been proposed. The main conclusions are as follows :

- It is possible to design a force field that, using the concept of charge scaling and a factor of 0.85, is able to describe with high accuracy the densities of a number of salt solutions.

- Viscosities are also described quite well for concentrations up to 3 m. At higher concentrations deviations are clearly visible, especially for systems containing a high charge density (Li^+ , divalent ions).
- The description of the behavior of the diffusion coefficient also improves when compared to systems using full ionic charges.
- Complemented with the Lorentz-Berthelot rule, the force field is able to yield quite good predictions for ternary mixtures of electrolytes, not used in the optimization of potential parameters.
- No precipitation or aggregation was found in the simulations performed at concentrations close to the experimental solubility limit. Thus the absence of artefacts in the simulations is guaranteed at least up to this concentration.
- The improvement of the performance in aqueous solutions has a cost: the densities predicted for the crystal salts are typically a 5% lower than the experimental ones. For molten salts the deviations are even larger, of the order of a 20 per cent.

Overall, the first impression is that the use of scaled charges improves the description of ionic solutions when compared to current force fields that use full ionic charges. It would also be of interest to determine solubilities and activity coefficients of the current force field. The overall performance of the force field for these properties remains to be seen. Further work is needed to fully explore the limits of this type of force fields. Although we used here the scaling factor 0.85 (which yielded good results for NaCl solutions) it would be interesting to check if other choices (i.e 0.70, 0.75, 0.80, 0.90) could led to force fields with an overall better performance. In the future we shall consider the possibility of extending the force field to other ions, especially anions such as carbonates, nitrates and phosphates.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

See supplementary material for numerical values of densities and viscosities obtained in this work for several salt solutions and for a comparison of the Lennard-Jones parameters of the force field of NaCl of this work (Madrid-2019 model) to that proposed previously (Madrid model).

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